

H2Avia - Hydrogen in Aviation

Project of the federal funded aviation research program (LuFo) VI-2, FKZ 20E2106

Supported by:

on the basis of a decision
by the German Bundestag

T2.2_BHL_01

Propulsion gas turbine data (preliminary)

AP2.2_BHL_01

Antriebsdaten Gasturbine (vorläufig)

Main Author: Markus Nickl (BHL)

Contributors: Fabian Peter (BHL), Christopher Warsch (BHL)

Completion Date: 22.11.2023

Confidentiality: public

Contents

Contents	2
1. List of Figures.....	3
2. Abbreviations	4
3. Executive Summary	5
4. Report on the preliminary propulsion gas turbine data	6
4.1. H2Avia technology scenario	6
4.2. Interface strategy	7
4.3. Data set information	7
4.4. Data delivery.....	8
5. References.....	9

1. List of Figures

Figure 1: H2Avia technology assessment scenario. [2]	6
Figure 2: H2Avia engine workflow	7
Figure 3: H2Avia aircraft synthesis strategy for the propulsion system	7
Figure 4: Specific fuel consumption in cruise part power of SMR Baseline engine	8

2. Abbreviations

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
APSS	Aircraft Propulsion System Simulation
BHL	Bauhaus Luftfahrt e.V.
CPACS	Common Parametric Aircraft Configuration Schema
H2Avia	Hydrogen in Aviation
ISA	International Standard Atmosphere
MCL	Maximum Climb
MICADO	Multi Disciplinary Integrated Conceptual Aircraft Design and Optimization
MTO	Maximum Take-Off
RWTH	RWTH Aachen University
TSFC	Thrust Specific Fuel Consumption

3. Executive Summary

The propulsion modelling in the LuFo VI-2 research project Hydrogen in Aviation (H2Avia) [1] has a high impact on the aircraft performance and the overall assessment of kerosene, as well as hydrogen in the aviation system. For that purpose the expert knowledge and modelling capabilities of Bauhaus Luftfahrt e.V. (BHL) are employed in the project to capture important effects. The integration on overall aircraft level takes place at RWTH Aachen University (RWTH).

In order to test the devised interface for the integration of the gas turbine performance decks of BHL in the overall aircraft design of RWTH, a set of preliminary data was produced. The main purpose of this data set is to test the compatibility of the BHL data structure to the RWTH aircraft design framework.

This report documents the H2Avia technology scenario, the approach selected for the interface, background information on the data sets and the delivery information of the provided preliminary data.

4. Report on the preliminary propulsion gas turbine data

This report documents the approach selected for the interface, the delivery date and additional information on the provided data.

4.1. H2Avia technology scenario

In H2Avia a technology scenario [2] was devised (see Figure 1) to ensure a fair and robust comparison of the hydrogen aircraft. This is based on three aircraft sizes and respective evolutions. The reference platforms the consortium agreed upon are the Airbus A220, A320 and A350. In the project similar aircraft are designed. Their designation is: regional, short-medium and long range references aircraft (REG-REF, SMR-REF, LR-REF).

These references are the basis for the incorporation of a set of evolutionary technologies (e.g. incremental weight savings or engine performance improvements). These evolutionary technologies are integrated to achieve a realistic application case for the envisaged entry into service and produce the baseline aircraft (REG-BAS, SMR-BAS, LR-BAS).

In T2.1 principle elementary LH2 technologies (e.g. liquid storage, etc.) were defined, which are integrated and produce the hydrogen aircraft (REG-H2, SMR-H2, LR-H2) and represent highly likely/low risk LH2 configurations (e.g. tube and wing, engine on wing, etc.).

The comparison of the baseline and elementary technology hydrogen aircraft is the main focus of the technology modelling, analysis and result publication in H2Avia. All methods applied to the X-REF, X-BAS and X-H2 aircraft are homogenous and comparable.

Figure 1: H2Avia technology assessment scenario. [2]

It was decided that the reference aircraft will use the RWTH engine performance data and the BHL performance data will be integrated in the baseline and hydrogen aircraft. The corresponding workflow is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: H2Avia engine workflow

4.2. Interface strategy

For the exchange of the data two formats were taken into consideration:

- Common Parametric Aircraft Configuration Schema (CPACS) [3] and
- The engine data structure native to Multi Disciplinary Integrated Conceptual Aircraft Design and Optimization (MICADO) [4].

Together with RWTH it was decided to use the MICADO native engine performance data structure since no other partners are participating in the exchange of engine data in the project. This is the least effort option for H2Avia. The interface is rather simple and depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: H2Avia aircraft synthesis strategy for the propulsion system

4.3. Data set information

Fuel flow and thrust values are provided for the three baseline and hydrogen aircraft applications covering the range of the typical flight envelope of the corresponding aircraft. The data sets contain two different engine ratings: maximum take-off (MTO) and maximum climb (MCL). The MTO rating can be used for take-off and go-around (i.e. up to 400ft) whereas the MCL rating has to be applied to the rest of the mission. Table 1 summarizes important propulsion system design parameter of the three baseline engines.

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Unit</i>	REG-BAS	SMR-BAS	LR-BAS
<i>Design Thrust*</i>	kN	20	23	75
<i>Thrust Sea Level Static</i>	kN	124	140	340
<i>TSFC (Cruise)</i>	g/kNs	13.53	13.45	13.11
<i>Max. Power Offtake</i>	kW	120	150	300
<i>Fan Diameter</i>	m	2.05	2.20	3.40
<i>Engine Weight</i>	kg	3620	3970	10650

**@flow path sizing point: REG&SMR: FL350, M078, ISA+10; LR: FL350, M0825, ISA+0*

Table 1: Propulsion system design parameter for baseline application

It is important to note that the propulsion systems are designed for certain flight conditions, thrust requirements and power offtakes as specified in the “DESIGN” table of the data sets. Nevertheless, the

reported thrust and fuel flow values are derived from engine off design operation at International Standard Atmosphere (ISA) conditions and zero power offtake.

Detailed key characteristics of the SMR-BAS propulsion system design are exemplarily listed in Table 2 and an illustration of the corresponding specific fuel consumption (TSFC) for cruise part power is provided in Figure 4.

SMR-BAS	Unit	Top of Climb	Cruise	Take-Off
<i>Altitude</i>	m	10668	10668	0
<i>Mach Number</i>	-	0.78	0.78	0.2
<i>ISA Deviation</i>	K	+10	0	+15
<i>Thrust</i>	kN	23	18.25	102
<i>Bypass Ratio</i>	-	16.4	17.2	15.1
<i>Overall Pressure Ratio</i>	-	55.0	48.5	49.0
<i>Burner Exit Temperature</i>	K	1750	1540	1900
<i>Specific Fuel Consumption</i>	g/kNs	13.88	13.45	8.64

Table 2: Key characteristics of SMR baseline propulsion system

Figure 4: Specific fuel consumption in cruise part power of SMR Baseline engine

Preliminary propulsion system characteristics of the hydrogen fuelled aircraft are derived from the corresponding baseline characteristic by applying a fuel flow factor of 0.3594 to the fuel flow tables. This fuel flow factor represents the ratio of the lower heating values of hydrogen and kerosene. A more advanced scaling approach based on a detailed design of a hydrogen fuelled gas turbine is intended for final hydrogen fuelled propulsion system characteristics.

4.4. Data delivery

The iterated preliminary baseline propulsion characteristics were provided to RWTH on October 13th 2023 and have been available on H2Avia exchange platform since October 19th 2023. The hydrogen fuelled propulsion system characteristics were added on November 22nd 2023.

5. References

- [1] Peter, F. N., Habersetzer, A., Nickl, M., Lüdemann, M., Ebner, K., Effing, T., Badrya, C., Haupt, M., Jünemann, M., and Möbs, N., “H2Avia – Project Description,” 2023.
- [2] Peter, F. N., “H2Avia – Technology Assessment Scenario and Design Space,” 2024.
- [3] Böhnke, D., Nagel, B., and Gollnick, V., “An approach to multi-fidelity in conceptual aircraft design in distributed design environments,” *Aerospace Conference, 2011 IEEE*, IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers), Piscataway, N.J., 2011, pp. 1–10.
- [4] Risse, K., Anton, E., Lammering, T., Franz, K., and Hoernschemeyer, R., “An Integrated Environment for Preliminary Aircraft Design and Optimization,” *The 53rd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference & 20th AIAA/ASME/AHS Adaptive Structures Conference & 14th AIAA*, AIAA (The American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics), Reston, Virginia, 2012, p. 44.